

the orbital quenching with the formation of an oxo-bridge of the type¹⁰, $\text{Cu} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \diagdown \text{O} \diagup \end{array} \text{Cu}$. But the complexes of DDHD show normal magnetic moments (1.73–1.82 B.M.) corresponding to the spin-only value.

The electronic spectra of the complexes are broad with a center at ~ 710 nm. This approximates to the distorted octahedral configuration¹² around copper(II) ion.

Thermal analyses: The thermograms of all the complexes exhibit almost an identical pattern. In all the complexes there is no mass loss upto 200° suggesting the absence of lattice water¹². The first weight-loss at $\sim 220^\circ$ in a single step is supported by an exothermic peak at the same temperature in the DTA thermogram. The weight-loss corresponds to the loss of two water molecules (7.52% against the calculated value of 7.57%) and the exothermic peak in the DTA curve indicate bond-breaking. Such type of thermal behaviour is exhibited by coordinated water molecules¹³. After 220° , the thermogram is horizontal upto 240° . Further decomposition proceeds slowly from $\sim 250^\circ$ with a final residue at $\sim 780^\circ$. The second step corresponds to the thermal decomposition of the organic constituents of the complex and the final residue to the metal oxide. The thermal stability of the complexes with respect to the substituents follow the order, $\text{Me} < \text{Et} < \text{Pr} < \text{i-Pr}$ etc.

Esr spectra: The esr spectra of the polycrystalline ADTH and DDHD complexes exhibit a single exchange narrowed line at g_{av} 2.08 with a peak-to-peak separation of about 110 gauss. The esr spectra of the complexes are comparable with that of the copper(II) complexes of *O*-alkylamidinoisourea and biguanides¹⁴. The proposed structure suggests an axial symmetry. However, random distribution of axes in the samples might have led to the observation of esr signal at an average g value.

Based on the above observations the structures may be proposed for the complexes.

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Polydentate Schiff Base Ligand Complexes of Transition Metals

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CONDENSATION of bis(acetylaceton)ethylenediamine with benzoylhydrazide led to the synthesis of a new potentially pentadentate ligand bis-

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crystalline solids, which were washed with a little acetone and dry ether and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl_2 . Analytical results show the complexes have 1 : 1 (M : L) stoichiometric composition.

In the second step, ethanolic suspension of the complex was treated with excess of veratraldoxime solution and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h on a water-bath at $\sim 70^\circ$. On cooling, the separated compounds were washed with acetone, dry ether and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were obtained in powder-form.

Structural Studies of some Mixed Ligand Dimeric Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II)

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WE report here the synthesis and characterisation of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} mixed complexes with 3-(dimethylaminomethyl)indole and veratraldoxime.

Experimental

The reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Veratraldoxime was obtained in a manner similar to that employed for salicylaldoxime¹ except that the crystals were obtained after standing the concentrated solution for 36 h at room temperature. 3-(Dimethylaminomethyl)indole was prepared by the literature procedure².

Preparation of complexes: A two-step process was employed. In the first step, ethanolic solution of the Mannich base and the respective metal salt was mixed in the molar ratio 2 : 1.1 : 1 and refluxed at $80-85^\circ$ for ~ 30 min. The light green, dark green, and pinkish complexes were separated as

Results and Discussion

Analytical results (Table 1) indicate 1 : 1 : 1 (M : L : L', where $\text{L} = \text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2$ and $\text{L}' = \text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3$) stoichiometry for the complexes. The compounds are not soluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMF and DMSO. They melt at higher temperature ($300-30^\circ$). The molecular weight data (Rast camphor method) of the complexes favour for a dimeric structure for these complexes. The complexes are non-electrolytes as evidenced by molar conductance data in DMF ($4-6 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$).

The magnetic moments (corrected for temperature independent paramagnetism) of the Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes are 1.55, 2.04 and 4.21 B.M. respectively. The observed values are less than the spin-only value for mononuclear octahedral complexes having no major interactions between two metal moieties³. The low magnetic moments of the complexes are attributed to spin-coupling within the dimer.

Six-coordinated Cu^{II} complexes possess two or more bands in the region 5-16 kK. The complex (solution in DMF) shows a broad electronic spectral band at 12300cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the transition, ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$, a characteristic of the distorted octahedral Cu^{II} complex⁴. The broadening may be due to Jahn-Teller effect, since the 2E_g state is susceptible to Jahn-Teller distortion.

Three peaks have been observed in the spectra of the Ni^{II} complex at 9450, 15100 and 25450cm^{-1} which have been assigned to the transitions⁵, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$. These are in accordance to the octahedral geometry⁵ around Ni^{II} . The value of ν_2/ν_1 is 1.597 which in agreement with the value

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Mol wt. (Found/Calcd.)
	N	Metal	Cl	
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{M}_{11}\text{NO}_3)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}]$	9.23 (9.27)	13.89 (14.03)	7.80 (7.82)	859 (453.02)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}]$	9.38 (9.37)	13.16 (13.09)	7.89 (7.91)	822 (448.14)
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2)\text{Cl}]$	9.38 (9.36)	13.02 (13.14)	7.81 (7.90)	804 (448.39)